

White Paper Workshop Report:

Best practices and tools for SoS applied to CPS applications

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Introduction

In principal, the purpose of this report is to show the points of consensus on common unique challenges faced by the CPS and SoS communities. It provides an overview to the public reader of perspectives on the status quo and helps guide support actions, for instance the consensus from this document supports the HiPEAC Vision with respect to the CPS application domain. There are many recommendations discussed, which are condensed into a short overview in the final section.

Refinements have been required in recent years on the definition of cyber-physical systems (CPS), to enable scalability and particularly ease of showing where and how advancements are taking place. For example, see the report “Collaboration on the foundations of CPS Engineering” from Platforms4CPS ([here](#)) or the more recent 2021 [HiPEAC Vision](#). Such systems may be distinguished by their physical interaction and coordinated collaboration. *It is important to be clear that CPS research is focused on the application, that is the product-side challenges particularly supporting the aggregation of technologies.* This covers a wide safety-critical domain, from transport, health, manufacturing to space. A rail network is a type of CPS, for example, it is an application requiring many technologies in order to function, such as AI technologies, but also rail-specific technologies. So CPS is a research class similar to railway networks, although a higher abstraction, it is focused on supporting the product (application) side and subsequently the technology side. The application-side research includes the aggregation of the contributing technologies and processes. It also logically includes supporting approaches to adapting the existing CPS – a factor that will be increasingly important for technology transfer.

Given coordinated collaboration is a major defining characteristic for future CPS, it means that System of Systems (SoS) technology will be a fundamental need for creating CPS. This will have several impacts and it is important to have specialist input from these two domains to confirm and consolidate where essential focus should be in order for effective technology advancement. Both domains risk scope explosion of research, so clear direction on essentials is important. A workshop was held with CPS and SoS specialists in September 2020 with feedback provided in this report (see appendix for contributors) and also contributing to recommendations in the HiPEAC 2021 Vision document. Already the importance of SoS for CPS has been recognised via the acronym CPSoS which has served as an important building block and to focus on the synergies and differences of these communities. However, given SoS will be inherent for future CPS applications, the acronym will likely be reabsorbed into the CPS acronym for next stage research, with CPS and SoS communities contributing to creating future CPS.

In the following sections, feedback from the workshop discussion is presented, followed by approaches for integrating SoS technology into CPS and general SoS tools that will prove to be very useful in the construction of future CPS.

Characterisation

Given the scope of CPS and SoS research, it is necessary to provide a contextual baseline describing these two fields of research as a point of departure. CPS is foremost an application domain, that is CPS is a railway network or satellite constellation for instance, so it is about creating the end product, which requires CPS specific technologies as well as SoS technologies and others through which it is built. This can be compared with the previously mentioned railway network research, considering research on the

aggregations of processes and technologies on the product side and research on the contributing technologies on the other side, including railway specific research. Both sides should evolve to support technology transfer. Just before going into some specifics about CPS and SoS, based on the previous points it is important to note that both are often the same product, but with different application-research focuses (e.g. a phone may also be considered a camera). Their specific technology-research focuses are also different with (broadly) CPS research advancing improved cyber-physical coupling and SoS research advancing the management of intersystem behaviours.

The most *distinguishing features for CPS are their physical interactions and collaboration*. CPS are products ranging in scale and diversity, from cooperating wheels of a car, to nanobots, to railway networks, satellite constellations, smart hospitals, autonomous car fleets, up to higher levels such as smart cities in which automation improves quality of life while improving resource usage.

These systems have six key physical characteristics that can be used for identification and which they cannot do without: *sensing, communications, physical action, processing, the provision of energy and coordinated collaboration*, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The six key characteristics to identify a CPS.

Classifying these physical characteristics is important not only for guiding research communities, but also in terms of understanding high-level progress across industry and for the public to be able to relate and understand the impact of CPS. A more complete and current classification of a CPS can be found in the HiPEAC vision document.

Systems of Systems are defined by ISO 15288 as bringing together a set of systems for a task that none of the systems can accomplish on its own. Each constituent system keeps its own management, goals, and resources while coordinating within the SoS and adapting to meet SoS goals. Their key characteristics were identified by Maier (1996) as having: Operational &/or Managerial independence of component systems, Geographical distribution, Emergent behaviour and Evolutionary development processes.

The different types of interacting systems are depicted in Figure 2 (Dahmann & Baldwin) and relate to the control behaviour over the systems. The last one is a more recent addition sometimes called accidental – this type will likely be very relevant for future CPS.

Figure 2: Types of System of Systems.

Most things interact in some way nowadays – if by internet protocol, then we call it Internet of Things but there are other means of interaction – this could be a very significant class of SoS technologies for CPS because these are more likely to involve unplanned interactions (such as electro-magnetic influences).

The way that one can distribute all the functional parts is very extensive and the SoS could be made up of systems that themselves are very distributed. For instance deployment of sensors in a city and distributed fog computing. There are interesting ideas here for instance as a user I might me walking around with a personal physically interactive system, which comes into contact with different data

providers as one moves around. A CPS could perhaps be changing continuously depending on its sources of information.

Overall, from the technology perspective CPS and SoS have different focuses, future CPS products will also be a type of SoS product. They share synergies related to technology transfer to the end-product. Note that SoS have another axis considering non-safety-critical systems and such systems would not be CPS products.

Contextual Examples of CPS and SoS Technology Advancement

Before arriving at the discussion sections, some of the existing European CPS and CPSoS research projects are presented. This serves to help provide further context following the characterisation just presented.

The H2020 project [1-SWARM](#) carries out CPSoS research. “**Integrated development and operations management framework for cyber-physical systems of systems under the paradigm of swarm intelligence**” The focus is on increasing the intelligence of cyber-physical systems at the edge of the networks, so that they show cognitive behaviour and have a high degree of autonomy. The EU-funded 1-SWARM project aims to develop a modular framework for designing robust CPSoS networks characterised by swarm intelligence that meet industrially accepted open standards. Dubbed the 'Swarm Intelligence DevOps Framework', it will aid researchers to engineer CPSoS for diverse scenarios: food packaging and material handling operations, automated guided vehicles in dynamic environments, and flocks of aerial drones used to monitor retail shops.

[CPSoS Aware](#) is also an H2020 project, representing “**Cross-layer cognitive optimization tools & methods for the lifecycle support of dependable CPSoS**”. Software is all around us – from smart grids to robotics and intelligent manufacturing. Cyber-physical systems embed software into the physical world. The EU-funded CPSoS aware project is developing a holistic and innovative approach. For testing in the manufacturing industry and with semi-autonomous connected vehicles, the project will design new models and software tools to allocate computational power/resources to the CPS end devices of the system by determining and autonomously generating what cyber-physical processes will be handled by a device’s heterogeneous component (processor cores, GPUs, FPGA fabric, software stacks). Making maximum use of artificial intelligence to boost reliability, fault tolerance and security at system level, the CPSoS aware system will also interact with human users through extended reality visual and touchable interfaces.

Moving on to CPS collaborative research examples in H2020, [SELENE](#) stands for **Self-monitored Dependable platform for High-Performance Safety-Critical Systems**: High-performance computing that employs commercial off-the-shelf components offers an alternative path to increasing the computational capability of safety-critical applications. Despite their potential in a number of domains, use of these systems is limited due to the lack of certified, reliable hardware platforms. The EU-funded SELENE project aims to change this by proposing a safety-critical cognitive computing platform (CCP) with self-aware and self-adaptive capabilities. SELENE’s CCP uses artificial intelligence techniques to maximise the efficiency of the safety-critical system and adapt its behaviour in different domains such as automotive, space, avionics, robotics and factory automation.

The project [ADMORPH](#) - **Towards Adaptively Morphing Embedded Systems** - considers the seamless integration of computation and physical components for supporting and building CPS: They have become the core components of several safety-critical applications, including smart grid, autonomous automobile systems, medical monitoring, robotics systems and automatic pilot avionics. Due to the

criticalness of the applications in which they are deployed, they have become a ripe target for cyberattacks. ADMORPH will implement a holistic approach towards enabling the safety and security of cyber-physical systems to detect and prevent potential attacks. The new fault-tolerant design approaches will enable cyber-physical systems to automatically reconfigure themselves in case of component failures and cyberattacks. Project methods will be tested in three use cases.

Finally we have [AMPERE](#) - **A Model-driven development framework for highly Parallel and EnerGy-Efficient computation supporting multi-criteria optimisation** -

Innovation in interconnected systems design is crucial for reducing cost and complexity in multi-component computing platforms. Current software development tools cannot fulfil the various antagonistic criteria in programming architecture. AMPERE's model-driven engineering (MDE) framework addresses this challenge. Their MDE framework allows for efficiency in constructing complex software architectures, taking into account parallel conflicting requirements. It also enables the use of specialised programming languages to accurately describe the subsystems' cyber/physical interactions. AMPERE envisages the development of novel methods and tools for constructing accurate models of proposed systems in computing platforms. Thus, system constraints are efficiently dealt with, while ensuring performance targets are met. AMPERE's computing software will also help improve overall system efficiency along with fulfilment of non-functional requirements.

Discussion: Meaning and potential alternatives to CPSoS

A CPS is a type of product, that is, a system to which technology is applied. This includes many technologies like IoT and SoS, but also dedicated CPS technology which, unlike the other technologies, is only applied to CPS since they are coupled with safety – a unique quality of CPS to other systems types. Advancements should normally call on us to question previous assumptions in order to evolve, based on latest CPS characterisation, the question arises if CPSoS or a variant, while in the present an important building block, will still be needed in future CPS development.

This is in particular since SoS technology is now considered a fundamental technology for future CPS. Based on the current CPS definition for future systems, it is unlikely that CPS will exist that are not also considered to be SoS. That being said, it is relevant to remind that SoS technology has other applications outside CPS in non-safety-critical systems, or interacting systems that are purely in cyber-space, or purely physical. It is a tricky distinction. SoS considers how a system is structured, a type of meta description which is composed of individual systems with their own operational purpose. Whereas a CPS describes the operation of a system – a physical system controlled by software. It is possible to state that there are several degrees for coupling or control of systems either in CPS or SoS. Of course there are also different types of SoS such as the directed and sometimes only a loose collaboration. So for instance IoT technology can be very relevant in some cases or not at all in others.

CPSoS is linguistically strange given you have CPS and you put them together and you have either a network of CPS or a system of CPS, which would suggest something like SoCPS. CPSoS can suggest that the CP is a special type of SoS, or that CPS can exist without SoS. There may also be finer distinctions – are the systems controlled by CPS, or do the individual systems have software control which are networked together. Given future CPS will themselves be SoS, we need to ask what is made more specific by adding the So or the oS? The origin of the acronym CPSoS was a very important trigger for enabling the two different research communities to come together and investigate their coupling (including at the workshop contributing to this report). While there are significant synergies, the boundaries between the two communities are important to keep as clear as possible and maintain in

order to advance technology at this level of complexity and scale. Their overlaps should be considered important collaboration opportunities rather than mistaken interpretations, such as CPSoS being SoSoS. A safety risk has also been raised (not currently, but in future CPS), because, while different perspectives may allow systems of systems, a CPS, especially with emergent properties, can only be a single system from the safety perspective. That is, they cannot be independent when working together, so one CPS subsumes the others (one system takes the lead) and they become one CPS (team) during the collaboration.

CPS is considered a good branding, with an acronym easy to say and when opened says exactly what it is, however there is a challenge on the visibility of the terminology, requiring more marketing. For instance a commissioner went to a workshop some time ago, asking at the lobby for the cyber-physical system workshop, with the response being “Sorry sir, we only have one for CPS”. Public awareness and also across technical domains requires work in relation to the branding. Some of the identity challenge is because CPS, and to an extent SoS, research exists as a duality. By necessity they are both about application side research and also dedicated technology research (remember the railway network example). This has been highlighted, with a definition crystallised in the most recent latest HiPEAC Vision document. More generally there has been less public visibility due to their use traditionally being business-to-business rather than business-to-consumer. Considering CPSoS has been known to raise the question if it is about emergency services. The various acronym extensions should be considered carefully by the CPS community. Wording is important and some communities have their own similar terminology but suffer from the silo effect. The CPS application-side research should support harmonisation across the market sectors and contributing technology classes.

When you put together multiple CPS, a more complex aggregation of CPS, the new composition must have its own digital twin, this is because the combination of the component systems results in new capabilities, implied such as in design time and deployment aspects. Different suppliers with integrated design added on top. A cultural gap in the market exists for understanding how to manage this complex design phase. Similarly we are also in need of new approaches for the aggregation of the multi-disciplinary and stakeholder research collaborations, particularly with the increase of decentralisation.

It is in fact crucial because of the different disciplines that have to work more and more closer together with more trouble in understanding each other. During the last years for support for design – support for mono-disciplinary has made much progress, it works very well and is well supported. But now someone from control engineering has to speak to electrical engineering, each having their own formalisms, languages, tools that are not accessible to the other. With CPS this is a specific challenge given the number of disciplines involved with also domain specific approaches. This is from the design side, but on the operation side humans are also key players where interaction with physically active systems of systems (CPSoS) is also a significant challenge. People contribute to the overall behaviour of the CPSoS, with terms arising like cyber-physical human systems (CPHS), or cyber-physical human system of systems (CPHSoS). Within the current CPS definition model, ‘usability’ is considered an important system-level property. A CPS common definition encompasses machines plus people plus processes. Any artefact is built for human benefit – humans are always in the loop. From the security point of view, sometimes a security procedure or solution is in fact human based and built only by a human.

The CPS community should be cautious about a proliferation of acronyms used in the common domain at a time where we need consolidation, and should be clear about what the added value is for the whole community, since proliferation has a tendency to dilute the focus of CPS as a whole. Of course shorthand remains relevant for specialists applying a technology domain to CPS, such as from artificial intelligence one might indicate this as AI4CPS. In particular terms and acronyms should be clear and with good visibility in order to consolidate relevant funding.

Discussion: SoS Technology Integration with CPS

This is both about adapting the CPS application-side for SoS technology and developing SoS technology for CPS applications. Terminology harmonisation and siloes are already relevant factors discussed in the previous section. Different communities are focusing on CPS-type applications, but with languages that prioritise their interests – there may even be resistance in communities to harmonisation in relation to this. Currently there is insufficient work across-communities producing joint and aggregating technologies. While this is something that the CPS community needs to advance, with a specific article related to this in the HiPEAC vision to bridge siloes, the need is also being explored through other initiatives. For instance, the Commission has the Pathfinder Research Programme (formerly FET-Open) and the High-Performance Computing HPC community is driving a Trans-continuum Initiative (TCI). The latter supporting the need to break siloes across the disciplines and sectors requiring intensive computing, these are seen as a digital continuum. Constraints, transforming security problems into safety problems. Part of SoS technology integration with CPS also includes the relation with the other contributing communities. CPS research focuses should be: CPS as an application, CPS-specific technologies, CPS-contributing (or tailored) technologies and CPS-promising technology.

Group problem->group solution approach. There are specific supports for collective research that need to be built up, tools for managing this are still very limited. Considering online internet forums, current implementations are not yet ready - they are mainly fit for individual can provide a complete solution to a problem, and see feedback that their effort is benefitting others (or see other benefits). There needs to be ways of weighting contributions to group problems with contributors seeing how their inputs are benefiting advancement. Wikipedia is one example that comes close to a solution, but even here individuals can block refinement of joint articles.

Transfer challenges. Technologies supporting transfer of collaboration/coordination into CPS (environment supporting technology transfer). Orchestration and optimization on SoS-level is a challenge, from the technology component side we are seeing levels structured such as edge, platform, and enterprise with services providing the interfaces. Technology-wise, we aim for systems that become aware of these items. Simulation and digital twin technology will be very important to support the integration of SoS technology in CPS, but will require working notions of contribution to high-level goals as well as of expectations on behaviour on the interfaces. Note that digital twins (DT) also has a challenge of a common concept but differences across communities and how they are used – so DT community would likely have a segment focused on CPS - in the contributing technology category. In such cases we need to have cross community work so the requirements can be extracted that will unlock the new CPS applications. In fact many people are contributing to building CPS without knowing it. Ventilators, satellites and drones for instance are embedded systems and may be used as bricks for future cyber-physical systems (given coordinated collaboration will be a required feature).

A domain of expertise needs to have several things: researchers; conferences; courses; a body of knowledge. Software engineering – people know this, they know what a compiler is what a program language is, what an operation system is, but also their specific methods and approaches for working together. One also has a general idea of the competences to expect from a software engineer. This is something that still needs to be developed in CPS, but with the added challenge that it relates to the combination of many disciplines (for instance see the programme for the International Conference on CPS). One is not considering something that is a box (like bio-medical engineering applications), but about aggregation and interfacing when considering CPS and SoS. On the other hand software engineering is itself an abstraction of different approaches and programming languages and the abstraction approaches are likely to also be relevant for CPS engineering. Another interfacing problem is with the environment, ‘situation awareness’, given interacting systems may have been built by different companies, (for instance operation in a hospital complex or in a field hospital). So we need to provide the means supporting affiliation of other domains with CPS and also that CPS has its own dedicated focuses.

As an example in the industrial automation domain, everyone has been focused on the individual systems because it was easier to manage in practice. These were digitalised with models, analytics and connectivity added. But a step change is occurring related to applying decentralised intelligence. This is a new paradigm being built, where some of the local decision capabilities are delegated elsewhere, which is in total contradiction with real-time control systems development over the last 40 years. Multiple collaborating systems is a balance between designing some aspects of the final behaviour\composition as completely centralised such as for safety and to guarantee certain performances – and decentralised aspects that include arising emerging behaviours. The big challenge is to find the right methodological approaches especially at design stage to minimise a disruptive contradiction between the two trends. Real-time control has at its centre the ability for deterministic response – the moment one adds an unreliable communication from distribution, an unreliable (non-deterministic) aspect is added which needs to be managed. There is a lot of interesting work to be done.

Discussion: CPS & SoS synergy challenges

Already from the preceding discussions one can see many perspectives that relate to both CPS and SoS technologies and with CPS as an application, including: The human perspective, non-functional properties like security, the technology perspective (e.g. computing, protocols, languages), techniques perspective (e.g. modelling), behaviour perspective, organisation perspective (layers/levels, aggregation, collaboration), knowledge, business perspectives.

Integrating humans in the loop as part of CPS and SoS is a significant challenge, because we are very much part of the environment including research from behavioural and cognitive sciences. We are the most complex part of the puzzle and so safety is critical. For instance, developing autonomous CPS that are safe and secure and can thus have a high level of trust from users. Here, safety and security are mainly, but not exclusively, technological, but trust is rather sociological. The CPS model should perhaps include the environmental modelling inputs/outputs. For positioning relevant funding good awareness should be promoted on maybe three distinguishing features for CPS.

Certification of complex cyber-physical systems is already a challenging task (e.g autonomous car). Integrating SoS capabilities will increase complexity, so both communities will need to consider how their technologies and combinations can facilitate the certification of the resulting systems. This relates to decentralisation of dependability and will need to consider for instance how security is distributed, if all the system components are trusted equally and where responsibilities lie.

Being applications, both are a destination for technologies. By destination, it is from the perspective of CPS and SoS representing something we wish to create through many contributing and aggregated technologies. A big emphasis by the Commission is research to adapt technology for industry, but there is also need for research supporting industry to adapt to technology, which relates to treating common application-side bottlenecks and also how to invest for longer term value. A contributing technology could be for instance AI models in the situation where some discussions can be taken centrally, whereas others will require aggregation over multiple systems with partial information. Some of this application-side support may be done jointly between CPS and SoS such as through a network of digital innovation hubs or through the Digital Europe initiative. From this application perspective, there are aspects of the EU’s Green Deal research that will be very relevant to develop for CPS, relating to how energy technologies are integrated into these systems, but especially supporting the adaptation of CPS production for using greener technologies.

From the technology perspective they are both a cross-section. Influencer of technologies/domains. Influenced by Organisation/Society needs and policies. That is they are focused on the way in which something is put together, so their adaptation (and industrial desire to change existing approaches) is related to many dependencies below and above these aggregating technologies. It is deducible that CPS and particularly the SoS aspects will be necessary for guiding the way in addressing sustainability challenges.

An example of the influences can be seen in the automotive sector moving to collaborative systems of systems through a servitisation process: services connected to cars; services operated with third parties out of automotive sector. This is represented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Servitisation towards CPS and SoS (courtesy of Renault).

Advancing the automotive sector in such a direction includes challenges such as:

- **SW (continuous) development cost** – Including SW integration, coordination with other development lifecycles (system level, product level), assurance of safety and security.

- **Risk of additional energy consumption** in cars life cycle assessment – including from increased AI, data transfer and processing, large scale development simulations, etc.
- **Human considerations** – such as user trust and appropriation by people in the loop, despite incidents.
- The **ability to prove socio-environmental global benefits** at territories level – design towards CPS and SoS without considering sustainability issues is likely to be increasingly difficult. Additionally, showing clear relations and impacts of such dependencies to decision makers and other stakeholders at territories level may be difficult and is likely a research field in itself.

While technologies with dependencies above and below them result in restrictions, there are many benefits, including that such connections are necessary to provide the most efficient solutions for such types of system products. For cars we can think about the garage for repair, or the supply chains, where anticipation of repairs can be managed.

Progress indicators for technology advancement and the industry pulse. There is general consensus that showing advancement in the methods and technologies for CPS, SoS and generally aggregative technologies could benefit greatly from a more tailored approach for research projects, and the way in which return on investment and uptake by industry is considered. At these levels one is often seeing diffusion of adaptations of existing technologies rather than plug and play (i.e. a company is unlikely to replace its product life-cycle with a completely new one). These should contribute to help the selection and deployment of the best technologies, tools and techniques in the best setting, where it includes processes that are being used for development, maintenance and evolution of the solution and the capabilities of the organisation that is producing it. These should contribute to supporting the optimum collaboration between the users and the technology providers. While many systems are context dependant the commercial environment has been driving classifications (for example directed and acknowledged SoS system types came from the environment of acquisition, which was concerned about the contracting rather than technical aspects). Such indicators especially relate to long term advances for value and societal needs, outside the typical shorter-term 3-4 year targets of industry, where this long-term aspect will likely need a supportive driven by the European Commission to investigate and establish.

Related to some final points from the discussions, it is very important to continue improving the ways we bring perspectives together and the relation with structure for features, stakeholders and business. Solutions will need to be developed in terms of techniques and approaches, that take into account the best way to convince practitioners to collaborate on CPS and SoS. Publicity for CPS is needed in terms of moving from perhaps a dry technical term to something the public can dream about and relate with. For instance a smart city would be an advisable example representation of a CPS, because it encompasses the many significant future challenges, with a good separation from roots such as networked embedded systems. We should reduce noise where possible avoiding extensions of the acronym where possible (in the public domain). There are many cyber-physical system advancements taking place without the awareness of the developers, as an example AI and Big Data specialists working with a safety-critical system development. There should be the means established to allow contributing communities to see how they fit in a big picture and relate with other communities.

Overview of the Recommendations

A summary of the major recommendations is provided below.

Given coordinated collaboration is a major defining characteristic for future CPS, it means that System of Systems (SoS) technology will be a fundamental need for creating CPS.

- Both these communities need clear direction on research priorities given the much higher scope of potential directions compared to other domains.
- For safety assurance, future cooperating CPS merge into one CPS (like emergency teams joining together for an operation). That is, one CPS subsumes the others (one system takes the lead) and they become one CPS to guarantee global safety.

Both CPS\SoS encapsulate types of end products we wish to achieve, so there are many common factors such as the human-machine relationship, showing the socio-environmental global benefits, tools/approaches to support inter-disciplinary development. In particular:

- CPS and SoS will be necessary for guiding the way in addressing societal sustainability challenges. This is because their focuses include the cumulative effects of technologies, system development and other dependencies.
- Some of this application-side support may be done jointly between CPS and SoS such as through a network of digital innovation hubs or through the Digital Europe initiative.
- A majority focus in research programmes is adapting technology for industry, but there is also need for research supporting industry to adapt to technology, which relates to treating common application-side bottlenecks and also how to invest for longer-term value.

CPS is considered a good branding, with an acronym easy to say and when opened says exactly what it is. However consolidation is needed:

- Treat the cultural market gap for understanding how to manage the complex design phase of aggregating CPS.
- Care should be taken about proliferation of variant acronyms. CPSoS has served an important purpose to bridge the two communities, but should be reabsorbed into CPS once momentum is underway. Clear boundaries are equally important for a bridge.
- Visibility of the application-technology research duality needs promotion.
- The aggregation of work from the SoS community to CPS, as well as other communities, will be critical for developing future CPS.
- The CPS domain should develop a portfolio of general expectations. These are for instance well developed in the maturer software or mechanical engineering domains. CPS has the added challenge that it includes the combination of many disciplines.
- Publicity for CPS is needed in terms of something the public can dream about and relate with, such as aggregations in a smart city context.

Currently there is insufficient work across-communities producing joint technologies. Initiatives such as the Commission's Pathfinder (multi-disciplinary) programme or the Trans-continuum Initiative represent efforts to advance on this aspect.

- There should be the means established to allow contributing communities to CPS be able to see how they fit in a big picture and relate with other communities.
- Tools and approaches that support aggregation of the multi-disciplinary and stakeholder are still very limited and should be advanced.

- Many people are contributing to building CPS without knowing it. Contributing communities should have a segment focused on transfer to CPS.
- Find the right approaches to minimise a disruptive contradiction of decentralised intelligence and the deterministic real-time control systems development over the last 40 years.
- Integrating SoS capabilities will increase complexity. Both communities will need to consider how their technologies and combinations will facilitate the final product certification.

Finally, the public sector will need to take a lead on developing progress indicators tailored for developing aggregative technology and for measuring the industry pulse. These are usually non-plug-and-play technologies where measures relate to longer term advances for value and societal needs, outside the typical shorter-term 3-4 year targets of industry.

Appendix

Workshop Attendees (and report contributors)

Jean-Luc Garnier	Thales
Alessandro Bagnato	Softteam
Yann Chazal	Renault
Maarten Bonnema	University of Twente
Michael Henshaw	Loughborough University
John Fitzgerald	Newcastle University
Tomaso Poggi	Ikerlan
Aris Lalos	ISI
Emmanuel Ledinot	Thales
Stefanos Skalistis	Raytheon Technologies
Carles Hernandez Luz	UPV
Ad Ten Berg	Artemis-IA
Eduardo Quinones	BSC
Franco Cavadini	ACT Operations IT
Afonso Ferreira	CNRS
Koen de Bosschere	Ghent University
Vicky Wandels	Ghent University
Charles Robinson	Thales
Stefan Van Baelen	IMEC
Marc Duranton	CEA
Pal Varga	Budapest University of Technology and Economics

Workshop Agenda

09.50 – Connect

Session 1 (Facilitator: C. Robinson, Thales)

10.00 Welcome

10.05 – Characterisation of European CPS (C. Robinson, Thales) 10'

10.15 – Characterisation of SoS (M. Henshaw, Loughborough University) 10'

10.25 – Discussion: Meaning and potential alternatives to CPSoS (Lead: C. Robinson, Thales) 20'

10.45 – Perspectives: SoS Project Overviews 10' each

- 1-SWARM (Franco Cavadini, ACT Operations IT)
- CPSoS Aware (Aris Lalos, ISI)

11.15 – Break 15'

Session 2 (Facilitator: M. Duranton, CEA)

11.30 – Discussion: SoS Technology Integration with CPS 75'

- Transfer challenges (e.g. system evolution, legal)
- Technologies supporting transfer of collaboration/coordination into CPS (environment supporting technology transfer)
- Group problem->group solution approach. (specific supports for collective research)

12.45 – Pause for Lunch 60'

Session 3 (Facilitator: J-L. Garnier, Thales)

13.45 – Perspectives: CPS Project Overviews 10' each

- SELENE (Carles Hernandez Luz, UPV)
- AMPERE (Eduardo Quinones, BSC)

14.15 – Discussion: CPS & SoS synergy challenges 75'

- Both a destination for technologies.
- They are a cross-section:
 - Influencer of technologies/domains.
 - Influenced by Organisation/Society needs and policies.
- Progress indicators for technology advancement and the industry pulse.

15.00 Break 15'

15.15 Other discussion points & Wrap-up 45'

16.00 – Meeting Adjourns